

Predictive Cloud Resource Management by Workload Forecasting with an ensemble of Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM and EL models

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Abstract— Due to the dynamic nature of cloud, many modern applications such as IoT, ML and AI based applications depend on cloud for deployment and provisioning. Cloud service providers (CSPs) need to provide the cloud resources requested by the consumer applications with high scalability and less latency. By doing so, the providers can achieve good quality of service (QoS) for their clients. However, meeting QoS with cost-effectiveness is one of the challenging problems for CSPs as the workloads vary dynamically. It is highly necessary to provide an accurate resource estimation and scheduling mechanism at the CSP's end. Cloud workload prediction helps the CSPs to efficiently manage the cloud resources. To predict the ensuing workload for a CSP, Time series analysis and forecasting techniques may be leveraged. These techniques show how resource requirements change over time and aid in identifying the trends and patterns in the resource requirement and hence determine the optimal amount of resources required in the near future. In this paper, a novel univariate time series forecasting methodology is proposed for modelling the incoming resource requests with respect to time. This paper experiments the ARIMA and LSTM models for building the prediction model. To further improve the prediction accuracy, an ensemble of hybrid of ARIMA and LSTM models and ELM was developed considering the cloud workload's inherent nature, the volume of the dataset and the technique's efficiency. The trace-driven experiments based on Google cluster trace dataset demonstrates that the proposed model outperforms the Prophet model in terms of metrics such as MSE, RMSE, NRMSE, MAE, MAPE, R2 Score on incoming CPU request.

Keywords— Cloud Workload prediction, ARIMA, LSTM, Hybrid Model, Google Cluster trace, Deep learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing operates under various service models, including infrastructure, platform, application logic, and data, supported by a pay-as-you-go approach. The setup of IT infrastructure and resource provisioning to the clients is crucial for cloud service providers. It involves managing and providing data and resources to users and systems. Resource allocation may encounter over and under-provisioning situations. While under-provisioning is less common, over-provisioning is prevalent due to cautious IT administrators, resulting in waste and overspending.

Under-provisioning leads to Quality of Service (QoS) deterioration, violating Service Level Agreements (SLAs), and impacting the end user's experience. In cloud computing, QoS is pivotal for a trustworthy provider-consumer relationship upheld by SLAs. These agreements align the provider's commitments with the consumer's expectations, ensuring reliability.

Efficient resource management is vital in cloud computing. It achieves SLA fulfilment, prevents resource waste, reduces energy consumption, operational costs, and subsequently, carbon emissions, promoting green cloud computing. Effective management improves revenue and profits for cloud providers.

Cloud Workload forecasting is a technique that facilitates prediction of upcoming workload. Queuing Network models and machine learning models have been leveraged in the past to forecast the incoming workload of a cloud. This paper presents a time series model that accurately predicts the cloud workload based on historical cluster traces. Time series forecasting is a technique that evaluates the trends in the past and forecasts the future trends based on the assumption that future trends would exhibit similar patterns observed in the historical data. Hence, in this paper incoming cloud workload is predicted from the historical workload. However, efficiently forecasting the cloud workload is quite challenging for a number of reasons (1) High Variance observed in the workload (2) Extremely expensive computation cost as the forecast requires processing of huge datasets. To overcome these challenges two time series models viz ARIMA and LSTM are considered. Then a hybrid model is evolved to improve the prediction accuracy. To evaluate the performance, the proposed model is experimented with Google cloud cluster trace dataset and the results are benchmarked with that of the Prophet time series model [1]

2. RELATED WORKS

The data of requests to the web servers from the Wikimedia Foundation was used as the dataset in [2]. The major attributes used in this paper include Average service time in milliseconds, Standard deviation of service time, Percentage of rejected requests, Percentage of QoS violations, Data center utilizations in percentages, Minimum number of virtual machines and maximum number of virtual machines and virtual machine hours. The proposed methodology was implemented through simulation using the CloudSim tool. It made use of the Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model. It is a popular machine learning model for dealing with time-series forecasting based problems that is best suited for converting non-stationary data into stationary data and for dealing data with trend nature. The methodologies proposed in this paper will also be applied in a prototype private cloud system.

CPU and memory demands of Google cluster were used as a dataset in [3]. The major attributes in this paper were timestamp along with CPU and memory requests at the particular timestamp. ELM-Extreme Learning Machine (a feed-forward neural network) model is used. In this paper it is observed that ELM substantially reduces the forecast errors when compared with the state-of-art models based on BhA, SaDE, BPNN, ARIMA, SVR and LR.

Cloud Insight model - an ensemble model of several baseline models is proposed in [4]. Multiple data including cluster workload traces from Google and Facebook, scientific HPC workloads from the Grid workloads, Wikipedia web traces from WikiBench, Wikipedia data, Wikipedia German page, Wikipedia Japanese page, Grid 5000, NorduGrid, AuverGrid and SharcNet were used to analyze the model. The major attributes made use of in this paper include job arrival rate, lifetime of the job submission and density of the job arrivals.

In [5], Google cluster trace data and NASA dataset were used. The major attributes in this paper include scheduling class, event type, resource request, priority and resource usage rate. MATLAB, Amazon EC2, Cloudsim and C++ were used as major testbeds in the paper. Several regression, classification, stochastic, ensemble-based and hybrid schemes are used in this paper. The following results can be observed: ANN and Wavelet transforms are used by many workload prediction schemes. Also, Random forest, Grey forecasting, Kalman filtering, Collaborative filtering, Autocorrelation was the least used scheme in workload prediction.

The datasets used in [6] are NASA and ClarkNet datasets. The key attributes of this paper were number of observations from past to starting of time series, actual workload in the specific time frame, predicted time frame. R tools were used to implement the proposed algorithms. ARIMA, ARIMAX, ARMA, exponential smoothing prediction algorithm and support vector regression models were used for workload prediction. In [6], the cloud provisioning architecture for web applications with a new forecasting model, Technocrat Workload Predictor.

An integrated forecasting method that combines stochastic configuration networks with Savitzky–Golay smoothing filter and wavelet decomposition to forecast workload at the succeeding time slot is employed in [7]. Google cluster trace data was used in the implementation of this paper. The results demonstrate that the integrated approach with Stochastic Configuration Networks (SCNs) attains more accurate forecasting outcomes and faster model training than several advanced forecasting approaches like ARIMA model, Back propagation Neural Network (BPNN) and Stochastic Configuration Networks (SCNs). accuracy and to explore more information in a workload sequence to provide better workload representations and extract more features.

A hybrid approach, which is a combination of an improved Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network and a multilayer perceptron network were used in [8]. NASA and Saskatchewan datasets were used for implementing the proposed methodology. The proposed hybrid model outperforms the other four models namely, MLPN, RNN, LSTM and LSTM-DE in prediction accuracy.

A deep learning model called - CP-SAE - canonical polyadic decomposition (CP) autoencoder Stacked Auto encode Model is used in [9]. PlaneLab, which is a component of the commonly known cloud simulation tool called CloudSim was used as the dataset. The proposed model CP-SAE achieves a higher accuracy than DBN and the traditional neural network for workload prediction of multiple virtual machines.

K-means based Rand Variable Learning Rate Backpropagation Neural Network (K - RVLBBNN) which is a combination of improved K-means clustering algorithm and Backpropagation Neural Network algorithm is employed in [10]. MATLAB Simulation environment, which provides a built-in model for RVLBPNN technique for modeling RVLBPNN as a supervised learning, was used as the major test bed for implementing this model.

From the literature survey carried out, it is observed that the key attributes used in the prediction models were timestamp, CPU request rate, memory usage rate, job arrival rate, density of job arrivals, resource usage rate etc. The commonly used datasets in the papers were NASA data, the Clarknet data, the Azure data, the Wikipedia data, the Alibaba Cluster data, Google Cluster Trace data.

3. ENSEMBLE ENSEMBLE OF HYBRID ARIMA, LSTM AND EXTREME LEARNING MODELS

In the proposed system, models such as ARIMA, LSTM and Extreme learning models were considered to build the prediction model.

A. ARIMA

The entire document should be in Times New Roman or Times font. Type 3 fonts must not be used. Other font types may be used if needed for special purposes.

Recommended font sizes are shown in Table 1. ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) is a classical method used for time series forecasting. It incorporates three primary components: AutoRegressive (AR), Integrated (I), and Moving Average (MA), aimed at enhancing prediction accuracy. To forecast with ARIMA following steps are followed

1) Visualize and Check Stationarity: Data visualization helps understand fluctuations. Stationarity is confirmed using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. Null hypothesis rejection occurs if the test statistic < critical value or p-value < 0.05.

2) Create Stationary Series: Trend elimination employs log transformation and data aggregation. Seasonal decomposition addresses seasonality effects.

3) Determine Optimal Parameters (p, d, q): Auto-Correlation Function (ACF) and Partial Auto-Correlation Function (PACF) help identify 'q' and 'p' values by observing where plots cross upper confidence intervals.

4) Construct ARIMA Model and Forecast: Using stationary data and optimal parameters, an ARIMA model is built. Training uses CPU request values from Google cluster trace data. Parameters with the lowest Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) are selected.

The workflow of prediction while employing ARIMA is visually represented in the figure 1 below.

The simplified ARIMA formula is given by (1)

$$(1-\phi_1 B)(1-B)Y_t = (1-\theta_1 B)e_t \quad \text{--- (1)}$$

Where B is the backshift operator, Y is the Time series, e_t is the random noise, θ_1 indicates the number of MA coefficients and ϕ_1 indicates the number of AR coefficients

Fig. 1 ARIMA – PREDICTION WORKFLOW

B. LSTM

LSTM which stands for “Long Short Term Memory” is a time series model based on recurrent neural network (RNN) model. It uses a series of gates contained in the memory blocks that are connected through the layers. For optimal prediction of LSTM, several hyperparameters are described. Some of the hyperparameters include the number of layers, Dropout regularization, Optimal batch size, Output activation function and optimizer.

LSTM is mainly used for capturing the nonlinearity in the time series. In this work, Adam optimizer was found to give the best prediction and linear activation was applied since the data falls under a regression problem. The LSTM model was tested for 2000 epochs with 2 hidden layers. All the hyperparameters were hand-tuned and the best of all was chosen to build the model. The LSTM architecture is given in figure 2.

Fig. 2 LSTM Cell Architecture

C. Extreme Learning Model

Extreme learning machines are feed-forward neural networks having a single layer or multiple levels of hidden nodes for classification, regression, clustering, and other feature learning when there is no need to change the hidden node attributes. These concealed nodes may be allocated at random and never updated, or they could be inherited from their predecessors and never changed. ELM takes less training time and is computationally faster than neural networks. Multiple hyperparameters are presented for optimal ELM prediction. The model needs to be initialized with a value given to parameters such as hidden layers Size, the number of nodes for the hidden layer. Then the input data and labels must be provided. The input weight

W and bias 'b' are chosen at random from a range of sizes. ELM performs better than the traditional time series models. The mathematical representation of extreme learning model is given by the equation 2.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M Q_i \Omega(x_j) = \sum_{i=1}^M Q_i \Omega(x_j, c_i + d_i) = \tau_j, j = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

Where N represents the arbitrary distinct samples, M indicates the number of hidden layers, Ω is the activation function used, c_i is the weight vector, i represents the number of hidden nodes of the hidden layer, Q indicates the output weight vector, d_i is the bias, c_i is the inner product of x_j and c_i , $\Omega(x_j, c_i + d_i)$ is the output of the ith hidden node with respect to the input sample x_j .

D. Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM Model

Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM is a combination of traditional time series model ARIMA and neural network model LSTM. Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM model was used to capture both the linear and non-linear nature of the workload. The process of obtaining hybrid model is explained below and represented visually in figure 3.

After making the time series data under observation stationary and deciding the optimal values for p (number of autoregressive terms), d (number of differences to make the time series stationary) and q (number of lagged forecast errors), the ARIMA model built.

The residuals - value difference in the actual and predicted values act as the training data for the LSTM model. LSTM handles the non-linearity in the time-series data better and also possesses a relatively longer memory than the Recurrent neural network. The residuals obtained from the ARIMA model are fed into the LSTM model and then the model is trained to predict residuals. Values set for hyperparameters of play a crucial role in the performance of the LSTM model. In this work, various values for hyperparameters were attempted to find the best fit. Adam optimizer was found to give the best prediction for the model and linear activation was applied, since the problem under study is a regression problem. At last step, the residuals obtained from the LSTM model need to be summed up with the predictions fetched from the ARIMA model. The sum obtained from the ARIMA- LSTM hybrid model is considered as the final result from the hybrid model.

Fig. 3 Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM Workflow

There are multiple ways in which ensemble models can be built. Some of those approaches include Averaging, Maximum voting, Weighted averaging and ranking averaging. In the proposed work, the hybrid ARIMA-LSTM model is ensembled with ELM based on Average, Weighted Average and Rank average methodologies. Based on the performance of the models, the Ensemble model with less error value is selected. The ensembling methodology of the proposed work is given in figure 4 below.

Fig. 4 Ensemble Methodology

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The validation of the proposed ensemble model for prediction is carried out using the Google Cluster trace dataset. A trace is a combination of several datasets, where each dataset contains a single table, being

indexed by a primary key that includes a timestamp. The schema of the google cluster trace dataset is explained in [11]. The trace combines the following datasets.

- Job events
- Task events
- Machine events
- Task constraints
- Task usage

Among the above datasets, task events datasets was found appropriate for workload prediction since it presented incoming tasks with their timestamps and the CPU, memory and disk requests. The schema of the dataset chosen is shown in figure 5 below.

task_events	1	time	INTEGER	YES
task_events	2	missing info	INTEGER	NO
task_events	3	job ID	INTEGER	YES
task_events	4	task index	INTEGER	YES
task_events	5	machine ID	INTEGER	NO
task_events	6	event type	INTEGER	YES
task_events	7	user	STRING_HASH	NO
task_events	8	scheduling class	INTEGER	NO
task_events	9	priority	INTEGER	YES
task_events	10	CPU request	FLOAT	NO
task_events	11	memory request	FLOAT	NO
task_events	12	disk space request	FLOAT	NO
task_events	13	different machines restriction	BOOLEAN	NO

Fig. 5 Task-Event Dataset Schema

The models were implemented using python. Major libraries used are NumPy, Pandas, SciKit, Seaborn and Keras. At the first step, exploratory Data analysis was carried out to understand the dataset, skewness, relationship among the attributes. Outliers were detected and removed. Model training was carried out at the next step. Data ingestion and hyperparameters were hand tuned for each model. In ARIMA, p,d,q parameters were fine-tuned based on low AIC and BIC values. Two hidden layers were applied in LSTM. Based on the complexity, dense layers and input layers are specified. Adam optimizer with 100 epochs and 500 inputs were fed as initial batch size. In ELM, hidden size was selected based on trial-and-error method to arrive at best fit. Input weights and biases were also assigned. For ELM, Relu activation function was used. For computing output matrix, Moore penrose inverse activation functions were employed. Each of these hyperparameters were tested with multiple values and the best fit was selected. Once the models were built, further to tune the performance hybrid model of ARIMA and LSTM was built. The nonlinear part or the residuals obtained from the ARIMA model can be modeled using the LSTM model. Once the individual model training was over, the next step is building the ensemble. The ensemble model was built using three methods namely averaging, weighted averaging and ranking. The three different ensemble models were compared to identify the best fit model. The best fitting model is considered as the final model for prediction.

Further, A decision system – implementable at cloud service provider’s end is developed. The decision system would indicate the need for the inclusion of additional resources based on the forecasted data. The decision system involves the following components.

a) Application Provisioner

It monitors the utilization rates of virtual machines at the cloud service provider’s end. The projected number of VMs required by the application is also received through the application provisioner.

b) Workload Analyzer

It produces a forecast of the application’s future workload requirements. Once the model is built , a simple decision making system is over the model to determine whether additional allocation of resources is needed or not. For building the decision making system , a threshold value is set. When the forecasted workload

exceeds the threshold, additional resources are added to the application provisioner module. When the forecasted workload falls well within the threshold, the existing resources are maintained.

Fig. 6 Adaptive Cloud Resource Provisioning Workflow

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical results obtained while implementing the above system are explained in this section. The visualization of CPU requests with respect to time is shown in figure 7 below. The forecasting results with ARIMA, LSTM model is shown in figure 8 and 9 below. The improved forecasting results are shown in the hybrid of ARIMA and LSTM models in figure 10

Fig. 7 Time Series Visualization

Fig. 8 Forecasting by ARIMA – Actual vs Predicted

Fig. 9 Forecasting by LSTM – Actual vs Predicted

Fig. 10 Forecasting by Hybrid of ARIMA-LSTM

The forecasting by the ELM is given in figure 11 and the final forecasting by the ensemble model is given in figure 12.

Fig 11. Forecasting by ELM

Fig 12. Forecasting by Ensemble Model

Five evaluation metrics such as MSE, RMSE, MAPE, RMSE, R2, MAE, MPE Score have been taken under consideration. The performance of the hybrid model and the ensemble model are compared against the performance of Facebook’s time series model prophet. The comparison graph shows that both the Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM model and Ensemble of Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM and ELM produce more accurate predictions than Facebook’s prophet model.

Fig. 13 Comparison of MSE, RMSE, NRMSE, MAE

Fig. 14 Comparison of MAPE

Fig. 15 R² Comparison

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, an ensemble of Hybrid ARIMA-LSTM and Extreme learning based models is proposed to forecast the incoming workload for a cloud service provider. A high-level framework for resource provisioning based on forecasting is also presented. The performance of the ensemble model built is validated with a suitable dataset and the results are compared with that of Facebook’s Prophet time series model. From the results, it is observed that the proposed Ensemble model outperforms the Prophet model for the dataset experimented. In future, accuracy of the prediction may further be enhanced by systematically tuning the hyperparameters of the candidate models of the ensemble.

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